

EFFECTIVE TEACHING METHODS IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

This article examines information on various methods that are useful for Primary school student.

Key words: cooperative activity, teacher-centered approach, gestures, innovative way, reading skills, involuntarily, listening comprehension, subject environment, Marry Riddles, action characters

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Introduction

In today's rapidly changing world, the demand for education is increasing day by day. Accordingly, a good deal of attention is paid to this field. The world we live today based on exact numbers and it is getting more complex day by day and education is the only way to understand the century based on accuracy.

The first step in fulfilling this responsible task begins with the reform of Primary education. In the lessons the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills, and abilities to students through exercises and students acquire the ability to use them as a result of mastering them.

Effectiveness Of Teacher

Primary school teachers play an important role in imparting knowledge to their students and keeping their classrooms engaged. Depending on the age of the children they teach and the subjects they deliver, teachers can use different teaching styles to help their student learn.

Education is a cooperative activity of the student and the teacher. Various methods help students during learning process, it includes receiving information, processing it, adapting it to the situation and applying the prepared information to life and in this process, the personal skills of the teacher are required [1]. Westwood, P.S. [p.33-35].

Today, the interest in using interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. We can see the effectiveness of these types of methods in the field of primary education.

Many teachers use different methods to make students interested in the lesson and increase the effectiveness of teaching. And in this turn, causes various problematic situations, for example, the appropriateness of the method to the age of the child, the number of students in the group, and so on. Choosing the most up-to-date, most effective, accessible methods for pupils increases the level of interest and importance of the lesson.

Methods

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One of the most used methods in the educational process is through action games. Such games increase the level of interest if they the students are lined up or standing up. This is one of the most effective and widely used way to attract the attention of elementary school students. [2.18-25]. This first of all, makes the lessons lively, increase children's intuition and eliminate hesitation in them. Action games involve all pupils in the class during lessons and everyone is required to be active and it makes everyone listen and understand the lessons better and it leads to rise the effectiveness of lessons.

Another widely used method is called The Ball. The teacher holds the ball in his hands and asks a question from assignment and throws it to one student. The student answers the question and throws it back to the teacher and the method continues in this way. This called by another name Teacher-centred approach. This is one of the most common methods of primary school teaching. It usually involves the teacher being in charge of the classroom and directing all the learning activities while the students passive absorb the information.

The teacher in primary class should be a real creator, the stimulation of the subject in the education process is created by listening, understanding, free and independent thinking, comparing, distinguishing, and classifying. It is necessary to control and manage the skill and abilities to convey one's thoughts and ideas to others. They must train with the moral and spiritual education of young pupils.

One of the main reasons for using different methods in the educational process is based on teaching students to think individually and to increase the level of being able to freely express their thoughts. Because of the most important principle in today's rapidly changing world is the expression of free opinions and it is possible to achieve better results if it is taught to students from the primary grade. One of the methods used by today's pedagogues very often is to show various cartoon, songs, videos during lessons. This method increases student's enthusiasm for lessons and prevents boredom. Students of primary school age can better remember ability moving pictures and various fairy tale characters, therefore, teaching lesson information based on such slides increases the level of effectiveness several times. Audio videos like these will further improve children's listening comprehension and reading skills. For example, it can be shown that children learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing it. While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the action characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

Subject environment

If the teacher can create that environment depending on the subject, the pupil will learn the topic better. For example: travelling, studying, in the birthday, etc. On the topic of wildlife, the teacher organizes a forest, information about animals (wolf, lion, snake, bear), what they eat (meat, grass, fruits and vegetables). This situation strengthens the student's vocabulary, language ability and expands their worldview.

Interactive methods

Another method is through gestures, facial expressions. When the teacher says something to the children with simple gestures, it may be easy to understand, for example, "Come here", "Close the door", "Open your notebook" or so on. To say the name of things these are visible and often used in everyday

life, for example: door, book, window, chair, television, etc. Since such things are always visible, the children learn these words involuntarily.

Marry Riddles is an important enterprise in teaching English by teaching students riddles, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to a riddle because of children are really enthusiast. [3.45]

Pantomime, in this the teacher tells the students a word and the student shows it. The rest of the students will have to find the word and say its English name. This game is more fun if done in a small group. It increase children's desire and activity to swallow.

We know that, children are curious. They quickly get bored with the sameness. So, it is necessary to teach them not always using one type of methods. Otherwise, children will understand how the teacher will teach and prepare for it. Teaching with innovative ways raises children's aspiration.

After the completions of any method, it is necessary to motivate the children in the class. Any small reward, for example chocolates or small gifts, will greatly encourage children and increase their confident and motivation. Absolutely, the desire to win will rise.

Conclusion

As a conclusion from the above, it can be noted that all stages of education should be organized in such a way that is teaches students to think comprehensively while providing them with deep and reasonable knowledge. Learning is not an obligation for children, but it should be formed as an interesting process that is done by desire.

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